

LUMPEN

A JOURNAL FOR POOR AND WORKING-CLASS WRITERS

Issue 14/ Winter 2024/2025 £6.50

LUMPEN: A JOURNAL FOR POOR AND WORKING-CLASS WRITERS

This special edition has been a collaboration between the Class Work Project and The Working Class Climate Alliance

Issue 014

Winter 2024/2025

Published by the Class Work Project

Edited by Emma River-Roberts and Zosia Brom

Designed by Lumpen & Seditionist Distro

Cover by Efe Levent/Mangal Media

Each author asserts their moral right to be identified as the author of their respective work

We printed this issue using an online print service because printing co-ops aren't affordable to us. All workers still got paid. But sadly, there was at least one boss involved in the process of publishing this journal.

WWW.THECLASSWORKPROJECT.COM

WWW.WCCALLIANCE.ORG

BUY LUMPEN: WWW.TINYURL.COM/SDLUMPEN

Contents

Editorial: Democratising the (Un)Just Transition	2
Emma River-Roberts	
Revolutionary Messages for Workers and Environmentalists	4
Vlad Bunea	
What is to be won? Risk, Reward and Working Class Participation in Direct Action	10
Kasmira Kincaid	
Just Transition as Green Colonialism: Voices from the Global South	15
Phethani Madzivhandila	
Easier Said Than Done	22
Graeme Fraser & Veldra Fraser	
This Is Where The Rubbish Lives	26
Si Egan	
Meat, Identity And Climate: Why Veganism Isn't A Universal Solution	29
Robert Căzăcuțu	
Love Is A Force That Gives Us Meaning	34
Tánaiste EC	
Growing Up In The Shadow Of Deindustrialisation	38
Tanya Rideout	
The Bitter Fruit Of Exploitation	45
Kevin Picado	
The Film Of Our Times: Working-Class Cinema for a Just Transition Worldwide	50
Vogysta & Fabian	
The Land of My Mothers: Towards a Truly Green Economy	55
Heledd Williams	
Building A Future	59
Isaac Bell Holmström	
Four Key Points Of Consideration For (Actually) Just Transitions	62
Adam Cogan	

DEMOCRATISING THE (UN)JUST TRANSITION

EDITORIAL

Emma River-Roberts

The just transition – a set of principles, processes and practices that aim to ensure that no people, workers, places, sectors, countries or regions are left behind in the transition from a high-carbon to a low carbon economy¹, has its roots in the North American trade union movement of the 1970s. During this time the Oil, Chemical and Atomic Workers Union advocated for a fund to support workers made redundant due to the environmental impact of their industries. The concept of the just transition has since continued to gain traction, evolving into a critical component of mainstream discussions on climate and economic justice.

Yet despite its ethos of empowering the world's working class, their perspectives have been broadly overlooked: the 2023 *Our Power* report, co-published by Friends of the Earth Scotland and Platform, surveyed over 1,000 workers in the United Kingdom's oil and gas sector to find that only 40% of workers had heard of the term just transition.² Similarly, interviews with Indian trade unionists found a deep scepticism towards it, viewing it as a Western-defined framework imposed on countries in the Global South, despite their unanimous agreement on the urgency of addressing climate change.³

Far from being isolated, these incidents are emblematic of a broader, global crisis of working-

class exclusion. How has this come to be? How has our social faction found itself shut out from discussions about their own futures? More importantly, how can we reorient our approach to ensure that working-class voices are not just heard but actively capable of helping to shape the just transition?

We begin by creating working class-led spaces for discussion in the climate movement – platforms where we can speak without fear of judgement or dismissal. For this to be impactful beyond working class circles, it must be treated on par to that which is produced by more privileged members of society. For too long the climate movement has elevated the voices of white, middle-class individuals from the Global North over all others – a structural injustice that we have a collective responsibility to overturn.

This is something that the Class Work Project, the cooperative that has published *Lumpen* since 2019 has proven adept at achieving, and I express my heartfelt thanks for being invited to co-edit this special issue with them.

Several articles in this edition highlight the need to prioritise not only the ecological consequences of production but also the rights and wellbeing of workers, to break the circle of worker exploitation that continues to plague the world's working class. Achieving this requires recognising and valuing workers' unique insights, born from their daily proximity to the workplace and production processes.

At the same time, other articles remind us that discussions must also widen to encompass the just transition's broader impact on communities. This requires a critical examination of how the shift from profit-driven production to one centred on social needs and sustainability will transform community dynamics – what are the specific needs of these communities, and how do we ensure that their voices help to guide this transformation?

A key theme running through this edition is the salience of working-class culture – something which shapes our customs, values and taboos. Cultural norms are intrinsic to who we are, and hold tremendous potential to inspire and reimagine a future that is both equitable and sustainable for all. Yet for far too long, large segments of the climate movement have leaned on outdated and one-dimensional strategies, engaging with the working class only through the promise of material gains.

This reductive approach fails to capture the depth and richness of working-class contributions and, in doing so, perpetuates a constrained understanding of justice. A just transition cannot be framed as a solely economic or solely cultural liberation. It must encompass both, because it

demands a synthesis of practical change and cultural recognition.

It has been a privilege to learn from this edition's contributors from across the Global North and Global South. I extend my gratitude to those who have written in English despite it not being their first language. The co-existence of American and British English spelling reflects the choices of each contributor, and serves as a stark reminder that the linguistic imperialism of English is yet to be dismantled.

Words and ideas exist as the initial sparks behind transformative change – may the words and ideas in this edition inspire you as deeply as they have inspired me. •

Emma River-Roberts, FRSA

Director of the Working Class Climate Alliance

1 Van Diemen, G., Matthews, J.B.R, Möller, V., Fuglestvedt, J.S., Masson-Delmotte, V., Méndez, C., Reisinger, A. and Semenov, S. (2022). *IPCC Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*

2 Harris, R., Jeliakov, G. and Morrison, R. (2023). *Our Power: Offshore Workers' Demands for a Just Energy Transition*

3 Mangang, N.M., Swarnakar, P. and Pai, S. (2024). *Transitioning Away From Coal: Perspectives of Indian Coal Unions on Achieving a Just Transition. Energy Research & Social Science, (118)*